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POWDER MICROSCOPICAL EVALUATION - INGREDIENTS OF *CHATURBHADRA*

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Abstract

Background: Now a days, the demand for herbal medicines has increased. Large quantities of raw materials are needed to offset the demand for plant products. In order to fulfill this requirement, deliberate or intentional falsification or substitution is sometimes done. So to ensure the quality of raw materials and products, analysis is important. Here, powder microscopy plays an important role in the authentication of herbal medicines. Powder microscopy is a part of pharmacognosy that helps to identify both the originality of drugs and impurities. Powders are commonly used in most formulations. The method of evaluating and standardizing herbal powder by powder microscopy ultimately results in the herbal drug's authentication.

Material & Method: Powder microscopy of *Chaturbhadra* was carried out. *Chaturbhadra Churna* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). Slides of each ingredient of *Chaturbhadra* were prepared using required reagents and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Chaturbhadra Churna* shows reticulate xylem vessels and parenchyma, fibers, fragments of metaderm, fragments of thin-walled cells, acicular crystals, epidermal cells, oil cells, cork, phloem parenchyma, starch grains etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic structures which are observed in *Chaturbhadra* helps in the correct identification of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). Powder microscopy is one of the easiest methods which helps in quality control and assurance of herbal drug.

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Key Words:

Powder microscopy, *Chaturbhadra*, *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.).

INTRODUCTION:

Today, the use of herbal medicines in the world market is widespread in all areas, viz. pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, nutritional products, etc. Large quantities of raw materials are needed to offset the demand for plant products. With the high demand for herbal medicines these days, pharmaceutical companies and traders often see counterfeiting and substitution. Thus, pharmacognosy plays an important role to control it and achieve a good therapeutic effect. One of the simplest methods for accurate identification of herbal medicines is powder microscopy. It supports the safety and quality control of herbal medicines. The simplest, cheapest and easiest method for standardization and authentication of herbal medicines is powder microscopy, which is a branch of pharmacognosy.

Here, for the present study *Chaturbhadra* is selected for the powder microscopy. *Chaturbhadra* is an important polyherbal formulation of the Ayurved mentioned in Raj Nighantu.¹ *Chaturbhadra Churna* formulation containing *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.). *Chaturbhadra Churna* is the compound Ayurvedic formulations prescribed in the management of indigestion. Pharmacognostical study accounting powder microscopy of raw drug exposed the quality and genuineness of all the constituents of *Churna*.

The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India has already developed the standards for single drugs i.e. *Ativisha*, *Musta*, *Guduchi*, *Sunthi* of this compound. Hence, attempts have been made for development of preliminary pharmacognostical profile of *Chaturbhadra Churna* (mixture of these 4) before its administration and comparison pharmacognostical properties of *Chaturbhadra Churna*.

AIM:

To analyse the microscopic features in the powder of *Chaturbhadra*.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To assess the microscopic features such as fibres, tissues, vascular bundles, starch grains, trichomes etc. in the powder of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.).
2. To compare the assessed features of herbal drugs with their standards mentioned in authentic reference.

MATERIALS & METHODS:

3. *Chaturbhadra* was used for the powder microscopy. *Chaturbhadra* is an Ayurvedic formulation containing *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall.ex Royle), *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) and *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rose.) were collected and powdered following the standard operating procedure.

4. Slide preparation:

Slides of each ingredient of Chaturbhadra were prepared separately using required reagents and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in authentic reference.^{2,3,4,5}

Staining agents: Safranin and iodine

5. OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:

Table No. 1: Powder microscopic characters found in *Chaturbhadra Churna*

No.	Microscopic characters	<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Musta</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Sunthi</i>
1.	Fragments of fibres	+			
2.	Tissue cell	+	+		+
3.	Vessel element	+	+		+
4.	Starch grains	+		+	+
5.	Crystal fiber			+	
6.	Tracheids			+	
7.	Prism			+	
8.	Reticulate vessel with pigment cell (Vessel elements)			+	
9.	Fibers			+	
10.	Oil cell				+

Table No.2: Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Ativisha</i>	Figure no.
1.	Reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma	Fig. 1
2.	Starch grains	Fig. 2
3.	Fibers	Fig. 2

4.	Fragments of metaderm	Fig. 3
5.	Parenchyma cells filled with starch grains	Fig. 4

Table No.3: Powder microscopic study of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Musta</i>	Figure no.
1.	Vessel element with spiral thickening	Fig. 1,2
2.	Tissue fragments with thin-walled cells	Fig. 3
3.	Starch Grains	Fig. 4

Table No.4: Powder microscopic study of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Guduchi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Starch grains	Fig. 5
2.	Vessel elements	Fig. 6
3.	Tracheid	Fig. 7
4.	Fibers	Fig. 8
5.	Crystal fibre with prism	Fig. 9

Table No.5: Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.)

No.	Characteristics of <i>Sunthi</i>	Figure no.
1.	Cork in surface view	Fig. 10
2.	Reticulated vessel with pigment cells	Fig. 11
3.	Fiber	Fig. 12
4.	Starch grains	Fig. 13
5.	Fragment of fibers with attached parenchyma and reticulated vessel	Fig. 14
6.	Cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains	Fig. 15

Through this present study information regarding the microscopic characters of the herbal drug can be known. For this microscopic study, powder of *Chaturbhadra* was selected. The microscopic characters of *Chaturbhadra* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle) shows reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn) shows vessel element with vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains. Powder microscopy of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.) shows, starch grains, vessel elements, crystal fiber, tracheid, fiber, prism. Powder microscopy of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Rosc.) shows, reticulated vessel, starch grain, fragment of fiber with attach parenchyma and reticulated vessel, cortical parenchyma embedding oleoresin cell and starch grains, cork in surface view, fragment of with attach parenchyma and reticulated vessel, reticulated vessel with pigment cell.

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Powder microscopic study of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle)

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Powder microscopic study of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn)

Fig 1

Vessel element with spiral thickening

Fig 2

Fig 3

Tissue fragments with thin-walled cells

Fig 12

Starch Grain

Powder microscopic study of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.)

Powder microscopic study of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.)

Cortical parenchyma
embedding oleoresin cell
and starch grains

Fig. 5

CONCLUSION:

In the present study, powder microscopy of the well-known formulation i.e. *Chaturbhadra* was carried out. The findings provide assistance in the identification of each ingredient of *Chaturbhadra*. According to the observations, microscopic characters such as reticulate xylem vessel and parenchyma, starch grains, fibers, fragments of metaderm and parenchyma cells filled with starch grains indicates the presence of *Ativisha* (*Aconitum heterophyllum* Wall. ex Royle). Microscopic characters such as vessel element with spiral thickening, tissue fragments with thin-walled cells and starch grains indicates the presence of *Musta* (*Cyperus rotundus* Linn). Microscopic characters such as starch grains, vessel elements, tracheid, fibers and crystal fibre with prism these structures are indicating presence of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Willd.), microscopic characters such as cork in surface view, reticulated vessel with pigment cells, fibers, starch grains, fragment of fibers and oleoresin cell indicates the presence of *Sunthi* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.).

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